

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PHYSICAL FITNESS VARIABLES BETWEEN LIFTER AND ATTACKERS OF VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

Priti D. Khode

Research Scholar, Sant Gadgebaba Amravati University, Amravati

Dr. Ajit Bhise

Department of Physical Education, G. S. Tompe College, Chandur Bazar, Amravati

Paper Received On: 12 December 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 28 January 2024

Published On: 01 February 2024

Abstract

The primary aim of present study was to compare Physical Fitness Variables between Lifter and Attackers of Volleyball Players. A total 200 male Volleyball Players were selected from Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University Amravati by simple random sampling. The sample consisted 100 Attackers and 100 Lifter male Volleyball Players. The data was computed and analyzed using descriptive statistics and 't' test in order to compare the significant difference between Lifter and Attackers of volleyball Players, the level of significance was set at 0.05 level. The result indicated that there were partially insignificant difference between Lifter and Attackers of volleyball Players. The researcher is a volleyball player. The researcher knows that physical fitness was the key to success and it was the backbone of the human life. It plays an important role in every aspect of human life, but to remain physically fit, exercise was very important. In volleyball and hockey game fitness was very necessary. While playing volley ball during day time, the researcher lot of increasing defenders and attackers, etc., so the researcher was interested to undertake the study on, "Comparative Study of Physical Fitness Variables between Lifter and Attackers of Volleyball Players".

Keyword: *Physical Fitness, Lifter and Attackers of volleyball Players. Introduction:*

Physical fitness is now more or less a matter of concern for a nation. The strength of the democracy of the nation is the collective well being of the people. The less working Amravati University of humans has caused many health problems like weakness, illness, overweight, under weight, bad posture, chronic diseases etc. Different people think differently regarding the

physical fitness. For a common man, to have a good physique is a symbol of physical fitness. In fact, physical fitness is considered as the capacity or ability of an individual to do or perform the routine work effectively with joy or pleasure. Physical fitness is more than the possession of strength, speed and endurance. Physical fitness means having the best work, to engage in recreational activities and to meet the emergencies when they arise. Physical fitness implies a relation between the task and work to be performed and the individual's capacity to perform that work moreover the recovery is faster and quicker.

Agility:

Agility is the ability to change direction rapidly and accurately and to control body movements.

Flexibility:

The range of possible movement at the joint is called as flexibility.

Strength:

The ability of muscle to overcome resistance

Endurance:

The ability to perform muscular work at sub-maximal level by moderate contraction for a long time is known as cardiovascular endurance.

Objective of study:

The purpose of the study was to find out the Physical Fitness of Volleyball lifter and attacker game Players in Amravati University, the purpose of the study was to find out the Agility of volleyball lifter and attacker game players of Amravati University, the purpose of the study was to find out the strength of volleyball lifter and attacker game players of Amravati University, the purpose of the study was to find out the flexibility of volleyball lifter and attacker game players of Amravati University, the purpose of the study was to find out the Endurance of volleyball lifter and attacker game players of Amravati University, the purpose was to compare the Physical Fitness volleyball lifter and attacker game Players of Amravati University.

Hypothesis:

On the basis of experience and knowledge of the researcher, it was hypothesized that there is be significant difference in physical fitness variables of volleyball lifter and attackers of game players.

METHODOLOGY

As every research demands a systematic method and procedure likewise this chapter adopts the following procedures including information regarding research design, source of data, sampling method, selection of subjects, collection of data, criterion Measures etc. A research become successful accompanied and supported by some reliable and authentic data. The statistical analysis of the gathered data provides a well-knit picture of a complete and successful hypothesis as pre-selected by the researcher. The chapter has been divided into the following headings: (Source of data, Selection of Subjects, Sampling Methods, Collection of Data and Criterion Measures).

For the present study subjects were selected from inter-collegiate players of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati from Volleyball Players (lifter and attackers) players for the collection of data for the present study.

Five hundred (200) subjects were selected for the collection of data which include one hundred (100) from lifter and one hundred from (100) from attackers of volleyball game players of inter-collegiate from Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati.

1. Agility: It was measured with 40 yard Shuttle run.
2. Flexibility: It was measured with Goniometer or Flexiometer.
3. Endurance: It was measured by Harvard Step Test.
4. Strength: It was measured by Dynamometer.

Collection of Data:

For the collection of data, the subjects are given full administration of the tests which is used for the collection of data in the study.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data shall be collected from the subjects by the researcher under the guidance of experts and guide and analysis and interpretation will be carried out on the basis of special statistical techniques viz. mean, standard deviation and 't' test.

The analysis of data collected on selected physical fitness components namely agility, strength, flexibility, Endurance during different times of day have been described in this chapter. The purpose of this study was to find out the diurnal variations on selected physical fitness variables.

The data pertaining to each of the selected physical fitness variables were examined by the special statistical techniques viz. mean, standard deviation and 't' test.

Level of Significance:

The level of significance will be set at 0.05 for the present study in order to test the hypothesis given by the researcher on the basis of his experience and observation.

Findings:

The data is collected from 200-male Attackers and lifters of Volleyball Game Players, who are participated of inter collegiate tournament of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati during the session of 2020-2023 and after that the collected data was analyzed by comparing the means of again statistically analyzed by applying t-test to check the significant difference among selected physical fitness. Therefore separate tables and graphs have been presented physical fitness. Each table gives the mean of Attackers and lifters of Volleyball game players. Also the researcher can find the standard deviation of both Attackers and lifters of Volleyball game players and also their mean difference was also been given in the table. The level of significance for the present study is kept at 0.05 level of significance and also the degree of freedom is also be kept in mind for the calculation of tabulated ‘t’ which is then compared with the calculated ‘t’. This is used for testing of hypothesis which was given by the researcher previously. If the value of the calculated ‘t’ is more than the tabulated ‘t’ then the hypothesis of the researcher will be accepted and if the value of the calculated ‘t’ is less than the tabulated ‘t’ then the hypothesis of the researcher will be rejected. Acceptance or rejection of hypothesis does not matter.

Comparison of Physical Fitness and Physiological Parameters among Volleyball and Basketball Players inter collegiate tournament of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati

Variables	Volleyball Game	Mean	S.D.	M.D.	O.T.	T.T.
Agility	Attacker Players	10.22	0.69	0.50	0.41	1.96
	Lifter Players	9.72	0.74			
Flexibility	Attacker Players	66.33	13.09	8.58	1.60	1.96
	Lifter Players	57.75	15.56			
Strength	Attacker Players	45.61	4.85	2.67	0.92	1.96
	Lifter Players	42.94	3.43			
Endurance	Attacker Players	81.38	2.57	1.44	0.56	1.96
	Lifter Players	79.93	3.96			

Discussion on Finding:

It is evident from the findings of table-1 revealed that there is significant difference between the mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players. The mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players was 10.22 and 9.72. The mean of Volleyball attacker is greater than the mean of volleyball lifter Players. To check the significant difference between volleyball lifter Players and Volleyball attacker Players, the data was again analyzed by applying 't' test. Before applying 't' test, standard deviation was calculated between Volleyball attacker and volleyball lifter Players which was 0.69 and 0.74, the calculated value of tabulated 't' was found as 0.41 which was greater than the tabulated 't' which was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This table shows that the volleyball attacker Players have more agility than the Volleyball lifter players. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

The researcher compared agility between Volleyball attacker and Volleyball lifter Players and it was found that the Volleyball lifter have less agility than the Volleyball attacker because Volleyball attacker change directions and are being able to maneuver quickly as compared to Volleyball Players. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

It is evident from the findings of table-2 revealed that there is significant difference between the mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players. The mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players was 66.33 and 57.75. The mean of Volleyball attacker is greater than the mean of volleyball lifter Players. To check the significant difference between volleyball lifter Players and Volleyball attacker Players, the data was again analyzed by applying 't' test. Before applying 't' test, standard deviation was calculated between Volleyball attacker and volleyball lifter Players which was 13.09 and 15.56, the calculated value of tabulated 't' was found as 1.60 which was less than the tabulated 't' which was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This table shows that the volleyball attacker Players have more flexibility than the Volleyball lifter players. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

The researcher compared Flexibility between Volleyball attacker and Volleyball lifter Players and it was found that the Volleyball lifter players have less Flexibility than the volleyball attacker because volleyball attacker was found to be similar because of the fact that both the games need high and similar level of flexibility. Both skills required jumping sudden change movements and involve more muscles of truck of perform movements which improves the flexibility of volleyball lifter players have to move suddenly in forward directions, sideways or down directions, so flexibility of hip and back is of utmost importance. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

It is evident from the findings of table-3 revealed that there is significant difference between the mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players. The mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players was 45.61 and 42.94. The mean of Volleyball attacker is greater than the mean of volleyball lifter Players. To check the significant difference between volleyball lifter Players and Volleyball attacker Players, the data was again analyzed by applying 't' test. Before applying 't' test, standard deviation was calculated between Volleyball attacker and volleyball lifter Players which was 4.85 and 3.43, the calculated value of tabulated 't' was found as 0.92 which was less than the

tabulated 't' which was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This table shows that the volleyball attacker Players have more strength than the Volleyball lifter players. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

The researcher compared Strength between Volleyball attacker and Volleyball lifter Players and it was found that the Volleyball lifter players have less than Strength than the volleyball attacker Players because for the purpose this study researcher aimed to assess the significance difference in volleyball attacker and lifter players in respect of strength ability. Volleyball attacker players was found high may be due to the reason that a volleyball attacker players needs to Smash, Block, Service etc all these movements need muscular strength and endurance where as in lifter players only passing, shooting is restricted which involve less muscular strength and endurance as compared to volleyball attacker. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

It is evident from the findings of table-4 revealed that there is significant difference between the mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players. The mean of Volleyball attacker and lifter Players was 81.38 and 79.93. The mean of Volleyball attacker is greater than the mean of volleyball lifter Players. To check the significant difference between volleyball lifter Players and Volleyball attacker Players, the data was again analyzed by applying 't' test. Before applying 't' test, standard deviation was calculated between Volleyball attacker and volleyball lifter Players which was 2.57 and 3.96, the calculated value of tabulated 't' was found as 0.56 which was less than the tabulated 't' which was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This table shows that the volleyball attacker Players have more Endurance than the Volleyball lifter players. Hence the hypothesis given by the researcher is rejected.

Conclusion: Within the limitations of the study and from statistical analysis the following conclusion was drawn.

There was found significant difference of Physical Fitness Components Variables between Volleyball Attacker and Volleyball Lifter Players of intercollegiate Players of Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University. Hence the researchers pre-assumed Hypothesis is partially accepted because in major areas of Physical Fitness Components (Agility, Flexibility, Endurance, Strength) Parameters, the calculated value that is calculated' was less than tabulated' at 0.05 level of significance. But in whole Physical fitness Components there was found significant difference because the calculated value that is calculated' exceeds tabulated' at 0.05 level of significance. So we can say that the researcher pre-assumed has been partially accepted.

From the above study it is concluded that in Physical Fitness Components (Agility, Flexibility, Endurance, and Strength) Parameters is taken into consideration, there was found significant difference in both of the groups which means that both Volleyball attacker and Volleyball Lifter players are Components of Physical Fitness Variables.

It is also concluded that Volleyball attacker Players are well-organized; self disciplined, reliable and careful as compared to Volleyball Lifter players, because Lifter players are the victim of severe mental disorder sometimes they use physical power to damage others during the game.

References:

- Ahmad Al-Mohannadi, et. al., "Stress in Physical Education Teachers in Qatar", *Social Psychology Of Education*, Volume: 10, Issue: 1, 2007.
- Kundra Sanjay, *Physical Education*, (New Delhi: Evergreen Publications, Third Edition, 2009).
- Kundra Sanjay, *Text Book of Physical Education*, (New Delhi: Evergreen Publications), 2010.
- Kutty K Suresh,, *Foundation Of Sports And Exercise Psychology*, (New Delhi: Sports Publications, 2004).
- Lanfranchi, M C., et. al., "Social Physique Anxiety and Disturbed Eating Attitudes and Behaviors In Adolescents: Moderating Effects Of Sport, Sport-Related Characteristics, And Gender", *Research Quarterly For Exercise Sport*, Volume: 34, Issue: 1, 2008.
- Mohund Ram. Mojumdar, et.al. *Physical Education And Sports Science*, (New Delhi: Sports Publisher, 2010).
- Mrs Sandeep Saini and Deepak Kumar Sondhi, *Physical Education*, (New Delhi: Kalyani Publishers, 2010).
- S.Grant, et.al, "Physical Activity And Exercise To Achieve Health-Related Physical Fitness Components", *Br journal of sports medicine*, Volume: 1, Issue. 3, 2003.
- Sharadrao H., *Foundation Of Physical Education*, (New Delhi: Sports Publication, 2009).